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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL AZIZ FAIZAN** bearing USN **2SU21HN001** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BRAND PREFERENCE”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KHAIS** bearing USN **2SU21HN002** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BRAND PREFERENCE”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL MUBEEN SHAFEE bearing USN **2SU21HN003** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BRAND PREFERENCE”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RASHID NAIFH bearing USN **2SU21HN004** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BRAND PREFERENCE”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMAD FAWAZ** bearing USN **2SU21HN005** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BRAND PREFERENCE”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMAD NADEEM** bearing USN **2SU21HN006** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BRAND PREFERENCE”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANADA KRISHANA** bearing USN **2SU21HN007** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BRAND PREFERENCE”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANSEYS A** bearing USN **2SU21HN008** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BRAND PREFERENCE”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANVITH** bearing USN **2SU21HN010** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BRAND PREFERENCE”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AIYUSHTHUL MUFEEEDHA P K** bearing USN **2SU21HN011** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BASAVAPRABHU HAVANUR** bearing USN **2SU21HN012** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BENO JOSEPH THEKKEMURIYIL** bearing USN **2SU21HN013** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHETHANA MANJUNATH IRAGAR** bearing USN **2SU21HN014** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG K P bearing USN **2SU21HN015** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING**” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAHAD A A bearing USN 2SU21HN016 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA REEWA** bearing USN **2SU21HN017** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMATHUL MUNSHEENA** bearing USN **2SU21HN019** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOKUL K P bearing USN 2SU21HN020 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HAMDATH RAZA SHIEKH** bearing USN **2SU21HN021** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY INTO THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT IN MARKETING”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHAL BARBOZA** bearing USN **2SU21HN022** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ADVERTISING: AN EFFECTIVE PROMOTIONAL TOOL FOR MARKETING NEW PRODUCTS (A CASE STUDY OF HH MARKETING COMPANY)”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARSHATH ACHARAYA bearing USN 2SU21HN023 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ADVERTISING: AN EFFECTIVE PROMOTIONAL TOOL FOR MARKETING NEW PRODUCTS (A CASE STUDY OF HH MARKETING COMPANY)” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HUSAIN FAIRAZ bearing USN 2SU21HN024 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ADVERTISING: AN EFFECTIVE PROMOTIONAL TOOL FOR MARKETING NEW PRODUCTS (A CASE STUDY OF HH MARKETING COMPANY)” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM** bearing USN **2SU21HN025** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ADVERTISING: AN EFFECTIVE PROMOTIONAL TOOL FOR MARKETING NEW PRODUCTS (A CASE STUDY OF HH MARKETING COMPANY)”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM KALEEL** bearing USN **2SU21HN026** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ADVERTISING: AN EFFECTIVE PROMOTIONAL TOOL FOR MARKETING NEW PRODUCTS (A CASE STUDY OF HH MARKETING COMPANY)”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj'.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JUSAIR M C bearing USN 2SU21HN027 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ADVERTISING: AN EFFECTIVE PROMOTIONAL TOOL FOR MARKETING NEW PRODUCTS (A CASE STUDY OF HH MARKETING COMPANY)” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAHAMMAD AZMAL bearing USN 2SU21HN028 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ADVERTISING: AN EFFECTIVE PROMOTIONAL TOOL FOR MARKETING NEW PRODUCTS (A CASE STUDY OF HH MARKETING COMPANY)” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMAD MASHAL ALI** bearing USN **2SU21HN029** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ADVERTISING: AN EFFECTIVE PROMOTIONAL TOOL FOR MARKETING NEW PRODUCTS (A CASE STUDY OF HH MARKETING COMPANY)”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEGHA A NAIR bearing USN 2SU21HN030 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ADVERTISING: AN EFFECTIVE PROMOTIONAL TOOL FOR MARKETING NEW PRODUCTS (A CASE STUDY OF HH MARKETING COMPANY)” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD HANNAN MOIDEEN** bearing USN **2SU21HN034** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ANALYSIS OF PROMOTION MIX AS A TOOL OF MARKETING COMMUNICATION”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD KALANDER BADUSHAH P M** bearing USN **2SU21HN039** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ANALYSIS OF PROMOTION MIX AS A TOOL OF MARKETING COMMUNICATION”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD MUZAMMIL** bearing USN **2SU21HN041** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ANALYSIS OF PROMOTION MIX AS A TOOL OF MARKETING COMMUNICATION”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD NAIMUDDIN** bearing USN **2SU21HN042** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAAHIQ RAZA** bearing USN **2SU21HN043** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SUFIYAN MIRZA** bearing USN **2SU21HN045** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD AZEEM** bearing USN **2SU21HN046** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIK PRAKASH GAIKWAD** bearing USN **2SU21HN053** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“MANAGEMENT OF EFFECTIVE SALES FORCE IN MARKETING ORIENTED COMPANY”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SALAHUDEEN bearing USN 2SU21HN054 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “MANAGEMENT OF EFFECTIVE SALES FORCE IN MARKETING ORIENTED COMPANY” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAHUL HAMEED NAZEEF** bearing USN **2SU21HN055** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“MANAGEMENT OF EFFECTIVE SALES FORCE IN MARKETING ORIENTED COMPANY”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms THASHREEF HUSSAIN bearing USN 2SU21HN060 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “MANAGEMENT OF EFFECTIVE SALES FORCE IN MARKETING ORIENTED COMPANY” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIKITHA** bearing USN **2SU21HN062** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“MANAGEMENT OF EFFECTIVE SALES FORCE IN MARKETING ORIENTED COMPANY”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms A MUHAMMAD ADIL bearing USN 2SU21HA001 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “STUDY ON ROLE OF THE HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT TEAM TO MAINTAIN THE SECURITY OF PATIENTS.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms *AMALGA MATHEW* bearing USN *2SU21HA002* has completed his/her minor project on the topic “*STUDY ON ROLE OF THE HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT TEAM TO MAINTAIN THE SECURITY OF PATIENTS.*” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of stylized, cursive letters, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ATHIQ ALI M bearing USN **2SU21HA004** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**STUDY ON ROLE OF THE HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT TEAM TO MAINTAIN THE SECURITY OF PATIENTS.**” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYSHATH SHIBLA SHIREN** bearing USN **2SU21HA005** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“STUDY ON ROLE OF THE HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT TEAM TO MAINTAIN THE SECURITY OF PATIENTS.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DILSHANA P bearing USN **2SU21HA006** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**STUDY ON ROLE OF THE HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT TEAM TO MAINTAIN THE SECURITY OF PATIENTS.**” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JERIN P REJI bearing USN 2SU21HA007 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “STUDY ON ROLE OF THE HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT TEAM TO MAINTAIN THE SECURITY OF PATIENTS.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JINU BABY bearing USN 2SU21HA008 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “STUDY ON ROLE OF THE HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT TEAM TO MAINTAIN THE SECURITY OF PATIENTS.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAHIMA B bearing USN 2SU21HA009 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “STUDY ON ROLE OF THE HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT TEAM TO MAINTAIN THE SECURITY OF PATIENTS.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANU BALAKRISHNAN T V bearing USN 2SU21BC001 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON MARKET STRUCTURES AND COST THEORY AS A TOOL BY THE GOVERNMENT TO BUILD THE COUNTRY ECONOMY” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAUSHIK KUMAR N** bearing USN **2SU21LS041** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CONDUCT A THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF A CONTROL TOWER IN LOGISTICS WITH A FUTURISTIC PERSPECTIVE.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KHADER HISHAM A H bearing USN 2SU21LS042 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “REVIEW THE POLICIES AND REGULATIONS IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MODELS OF THE UK FROM THE TRANSPORT PERSPECTIVE.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KRISHNAPRIYA K bearing USN 2SU21LS043 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “REVIEW THE POLICIES AND REGULATIONS IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MODELS OF THE UK FROM THE TRANSPORT PERSPECTIVE.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **M MAHAMMAD ANSAF SANAL** bearing USN **2SU21LS044** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“REVIEW THE POLICIES AND REGULATIONS IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MODELS OF THE UK FROM THE TRANSPORT PERSPECTIVE.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANASA T SANIL bearing USN 2SU21LS045 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “REVIEW THE POLICIES AND REGULATIONS IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MODELS OF THE UK FROM THE TRANSPORT PERSPECTIVE.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MARSHAD B M bearing USN 2SU21LS046 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “REVIEW THE POLICIES AND REGULATIONS IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MODELS OF THE UK FROM THE TRANSPORT PERSPECTIVE.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED LIYA UDDIN. P** bearing USN **2SU21LS053** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“PREPARE A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE ETHICAL PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MATHAF** bearing USN **2SU21LS054** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“PREPARE A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE ETHICAL PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NASEEM** bearing USN **2SU21LS055** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“PREPARE A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE ETHICAL PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAMAL.PK** bearing USN **2SU21LS062** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED THANSEEL M** bearing USN **2SU21LS063** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED THOUSEED N M** bearing USN **2SU21LS064** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD AHAMMED KUNHI** bearing USN **2SU21LS066** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHYADEEN SHAHEEN bearing USN 2SU21LS069 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDAGOPAL K bearing USN 2SU21LS070 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAWAF AHMED SHEIKH bearing USN **2SU21LS071** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.**” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIGHIL P S bearing USN 2SU21LS072 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIRANJANAA A bearing USN **2SU21LS073** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.**” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms P T ANANDU KRISHNA bearing USN 2SU21LS074 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAADUNNIZAM** bearing USN **2SU21LS076** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SADAF IBRAHIM bearing USN 2SU21LS077 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SALMAN HASHIM A K bearing USN 2SU21LS078 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ANALYZE THE INFLUENCE OF IT INNOVATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAHIN MOHAMMED NASAR** bearing USN **2SU21LS082** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ANALYZE THE COST FACTORS IN LOGISTICS.”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARJUN KARTHIKEYAN bearing USN 2SU21PM025 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SECURITY AGENTS IN PORTS” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHID MANU K** bearing USN **2SU21PM027** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SECURITY AGENTS IN PORTS”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN A S** bearing USN **2SU21PM028** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SECURITY AGENTS IN PORTS”** in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms *ATHUL KRISHNA P* bearing USN *2SU21PM030* has completed his/her minor project on the topic “*AN ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTION IN THE INDIAN MARITIME INDUSTRY*” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHINTHU SAJI JOSEPH bearing USN 2SU21PM034 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “AN ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTION IN THE INDIAN MARITIME INDUSTRY” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEERAJ bearing USN 2SU21PM035 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “AN ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTION IN THE INDIAN MARITIME INDUSTRY” in the First year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce